

MULTISCALE MODELLING OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF WOVEN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

The present paper proposes a multiscale model of the mechanical behaviour of woven composite materials. The DMD model is based on a physical description of the reinforcement geometry of the material and the damage mechanisms. The model is applied to a woven-ceramic-matrix composite material and its predictive capabilities are investigated.

Keywords: Textile composites, damage mechanics, multiscale modelling, ceramic-matrix composites.

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in the use of textile architectures for advanced composite applications. They offer a number of attractive properties compared to their non-woven counterparts, such as improved inter-laminar properties and impact resistance. However, their complex and multiscale architecture (Fig. 1) makes the analysis and the modelling of their behaviour quite challenging. Most of the available models for woven composites are based on continuum damage mechanics. They can provide a good approximation of the overall response of the material but do not take into account their specificities. And despite many attempts to develop effective models for woven composites, there is currently no approach that can accurately capture all of the important aspects of fabric deformation and effectively predict both the macroscopic non-linear mechanical response, as well as the response of the constituents at the micro and mesostructural level.

Recently, multiscale damage models based on micromechanical considerations have been developed for composite laminates [1, 2]. In these models, the effective macroscopic non-linear behaviour of the material is derived from the numerical homogenization of representative unit cells. The extension of such modelling approaches from unidirectional laminates to complex multilayer woven materials

requires the development of (i) an appropriate multiscale modelling framework and (ii) specialized numerical

Figure 1: Typical microstructure of a woven composite material: scale of the textile reinforcement – mesoscale (*left*) and scale of a yarn – microscale (*right*).

The purpose of the present paper is to introduce a multiscale modelling approach based on a physical description of the geometry of the woven reinforcement, the properties of the constituents and their damage mechanics for the derivation of the effective macroscopic constitutive behaviour of woven composite materials.

THE DISCRETE MICRO DAMAGE (DMD) FRAMEWORK

Damage modelling

The DMD damage model is written at the macroscopic scale in the framework of the continuum damage mechanics. A major difference with the other classic macroscopic damage models emerges from the nature of the damage variables. Here, the internal state variables are chosen to directly measure the state of the microstructural damage instead of just measuring a loss of elastic properties. In the DMD approach, the damage variables are defined as crack densities and interfacial debonded areas. Thus, the effective elastic stiffness tensor $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ is directly defined from a set of micromechanical damage variables (d_1, \dots, d_n) :

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = f(d_1, \dots, d_n)$$

The effective elastic strain energy can then be written as follows :

$$2\rho\psi = (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{e}^0 - \mathbf{e}^{th}) : \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{e}^0 - \mathbf{e}^{th}) + (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{e}^0 - \mathbf{e}^{th}) : \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^0 : \mathbf{e}^0 + \mathbf{e}^0 : \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^0 : (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{e}^0 - \mathbf{e}^{th}) ,$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}^0$ are respectively the effective elastic stiffness tensor and the initial elastic stiffness tensor, \mathbf{e} is the total strain, \mathbf{e}^{th} the thermal strain and \mathbf{e}^0 is the residual inelastic strain.

The effective elastic stiffness tensor $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ is related to the damage variables d_i through a damage effect tensor \mathbf{D}

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = (\mathbf{C}^0 - \mathbf{D}(d_1, \dots, d_n))$$

The damage effect tensor \mathbf{D} is defined as

$$\mathbf{D} = D_{ij} = h_{ij}(\eta_1 d_1, \dots, \eta_n d_n) \cdot C_{ij}^0$$

where h_{ij} represents the relative variation of the (i,j)-component of the stiffness tensor for a damage state (d_1, \dots, d_n) and η_k is a damage deactivation index allowing the partial or complete recovery of the initial elastic stiffness under a reverse loading.

This formulation allows one to obtain an effective macroscopic behaviour law through the derivation of the effective strain energy that is defined from a micromechanical description of the damage state. The scale transition is performed through the evaluation of the damage effect tensor \mathbf{D} . Hence, the main step of the derivation of the behaviour law consists in the estimation of the damage effect tensor.

Numerical evaluation of the damage effect tensor

The damage effect tensor is evaluated numerically using a finite element (FE) homogenization procedure similar to [3]. Specific damage configurations are introduced in a discrete manner into finite element periodic cells that are representative of the microstructure of the material, i.e. cracks and debonding surfaces are generated in the finite element meshes of these cells. The effect of the damage on the effective elastic properties $h_{ij}(d_1, \dots, d_n)$ is evaluated using a standard finite element homogenization procedure. Finally, the computed values of h_{ij} are interpolated over the whole damage space (d_1, \dots, d_n) and the evolution of the macroscopic damage effect tensor \mathbf{D} is fitted as a function of the microscopic damage variables (d_1, \dots, d_n) .

This numerical procedure is based on the homogenization of damaged unit cells and thus requires generating representative cells of the microstructure of the material at different scales. One must be able to determine geometrical and morphological properties of the microstructure of the material, and then have to create finite element meshes of representative unit cells.

CONSTRUCTION OF REPRESENTATIVE UNIT CELLS

Construction of representative unit cells at the microscale

The morphology of the microstructure at the microscale is governed by the pseudo-random arrangement of the fibres (Fig 2). Statistical descriptors like covariance [4] could here be used to quantify the heterogeneity of the microstructure.

Representative unit cell could then be constructed using this statistical information. Given an initial random distribution of N fibres inside a unit cell, the fibre positions are optimized until the covariance of the unit cell replicates the one from the complete microstructure. At the end of this iterative optimization process, the unit cell has a covariance similar to the microstructure one and can be considered as statistically representative of the whole microstructure. Once the position of the fibres is determined, it is straightforward to add the interphase and the matrix layers around the fibres and to generate a FE mesh of the representative unit cell (Fig 2).

Figure 2: Typical microstructure of a yarn (*left*), covariance-optimal fibre positions (*center*), and finite element mesh of a representative cell (*right*)

The geometrical and mechanical representativity of these covariance-optimized unit cells has been investigated for a growing number of fibres. It has been shown that unit cells containing only 20 to 30 fibres are sufficient to obtain a good overall estimation of the effective elastic properties of a yarn that are made of several hundreds of fibres [5].

Construction of representative unit cells at the mesoscale

The construction of unit cells at the mesoscale is a two-step procedure. First, the geometry of the woven reinforcement is modelled from the yarns interleaving sequence and their geometrical properties. The total bending energy of the textile reinforcement is minimized to calculate its internal geometry in a relaxed state. This geometrical model is then transformed into a volumic FE mesh of the reinforcement.

Figure 3: Representative unit cell of a woven ceramic matrix composite material.

The second step consists in generating a volumic model of the matrix at the mesoscale. In the case of ceramic matrix composite, the matrix is made of a thin layer deposited almost uniformly around the yarns. Thus, the volumic FE meshes of the yarns are first dilated by the thickness of the layer of matrix. Then the inner part corresponding to the yarns initial volume is removed, and the new entity is remeshed accordingly. All the Boolean operations (union, difference) between the volumes are performed directly on

the FE meshes as in [6]. The FE mesh of the representative unit cell is finally obtained by merging the yarns meshes and the matrix mesh (Fig. 3).

APPLICATION OF THE DMD MODEL TO A WOVEN CERAMIC-MATRIX COMPOSITE

Identification of the damage effect tensor

The DMD approach has been applied to a multilayer woven ceramic-matrix composite (CMC). The damage mechanisms that have been observed experimentally for CMC materials are (i) intra-yarns matrix microcracking and (ii) fibre breaking at the microscale, and (iii) inter-yarns matrix cracking and (iv) transverse yarns cracking at the mesoscale (Fig. 4). It is worth noting that each elementary damage mechanism is accompanied by debonding at the fibre/matrix and yarn/matrix interfaces.

Figure 4: Illustration of the elementary damage mechanisms at the mesoscale.

A damage variable is introduced for each elementary damage mechanism. The damage variables are defined in terms of crack density and debonded area. It is important to remark that for this specific CMC material the damage is always orientated by the directions of the reinforcement, whatever the direction of the loading is, which dramatically reduces the number of possible damage configurations.

As discussed earlier, the damage effect tensor is identified using representative unit cells at the micro and mesoscale in which damage has been introduced (Fig 5). The damaged yarns are supposed to be homogeneous at the mesoscale. Their effective properties are computed from the homogenization of representative unit cells at the microscale. These properties are then used for the computation of the effective properties of the material at the mesoscale. The damage effects h_{ij} are then obtained as functions of the elementary damage mechanisms variables (Fig 6). The damage effect tensor \mathbf{D} can then be directly computed from these response surfaces for any damage configuration.

Figure 5: Finite element meshes of representative unit cells at the microscale (*left*) and at the mesoscale (*right*). Note that some cracks and interfacial debonding have been introduced in the mesh of the mesoscopic unit cell.

Figure 6: Evolution of the damage effect tensor components h_{ij} as a function of two micro damage variables (d_1^n, d_2^n) corresponding to inter-yarns matrix cracking.

Identification of the damage kinematics

The damage kinematics, i.e. the evolution of the damage variables versus the applied load, has been identified on a monotonic tensile test in the axis of the woven reinforcement (Fig. 7). An inverse method has been used to determine the optimal numerical values of the parameters of the damage kinematics functions.

Figure 7: Experimental (*solid line*) and identified (*circle markers*) stress-strain curves for a monotonic tensile test in the direction of the reinforcement axis.

Moreover, the physical admissibility of the identified kinematics have been validated thanks to *in-situ* experimental micrographic observations of the crack patterns during tensile tests on polished specimens.

Validation of the DMD model

The predictive character of the DMD model has been investigated by simulating off-axis tensile tests, which from the material point of view are a combination of tensile and shear loading. The stress-strain curves of simulated 45° and 22.5° off-axis tests are depicted in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Experimental (*solid line*) and simulated (*circle markers*) stress-strain curves for off-axis monotonic tensile tests at 45° (*left*) and 22.5° (*right*).

The results show a good agreement between the stress-strain curves simulated with the DMD model and the experimental results. One has to remind here that the identification

of the parameters of the damage kinematics are performed on only one monotonic on-axis tensile test. Hence, the numerical multiscale identification of the damage effects accurately predicts the tensile-shear couplings and their effect on the effective behaviour of the material. These couplings are directly determined by the previously computed damage effect response surfaces, without the need for introducing any extra material parameters.

Application of the DMD model to a structural test

The DMD has been implemented into the general finite element code ZeBuLoN [7] and applied to small industrial structural tests, namely a tensile test on a shifted double-notched specimen, a torsion test on a holed plate and a flexure test on a L-angle corner.

Figure 9: Experimental (*solid line*) and simulated (*reference macroscopic model with square markers and DMD model with circle markers*) load-strain curves for a tensile test on a CMC shifted double-notched specimen.

The DMD simulation results have been compared to those obtained with a reference macroscopic model [8] for the same structural tests. In all the investigated cases, the global response of the structure simulated with the DMD model is close to the experimental one, and at least as accurate as the results obtained with the reference macroscopic model (see for instance, Fig. 9)

Moreover, as the damage variables of the DMD model directly represent the micromechanical damage, one can immediately access to the local evolution of the crack densities, which is not possible with a purely macroscopic model. As an example, the evolution of the inter-yarns matrix crack density for the shifted double-notched specimen tensile test is depicted in Fig. 10. The crack density is found to be maximal in the centre zone between the notches, which corresponds to the fracture zone of the specimen (Fig. 11). This micromechanics-based character increases the confidence of

the results obtained with the DMD model since the simulations could be compared with the experiments, not only in terms of global structural response, but also in terms of local damage-driven microstructural evolution. This could also be of great interest for further extensions of the DMD model to the simulation of thermo-mechanical fatigue loadings under oxidizing atmosphere, which requires an accurate local description of the evolution of the microstructure of the material.

Figure 10: Evolution of the inter-yarns matrix cracks density (mm^{-1}) for the shifted double-notched specimen tensile test. The corresponding applied loads are $F=2270N$ (*left*), $F=4140N$ (*centre*), and $F=5320N$ (*right*).

Figure 11: Fracture pattern of the shifted double-notched specimen.

CONCLUSION

A multiscale model of the mechanical behaviour of woven composite materials has been proposed. The DMD model is based on a physical description and modelling of the material microstructure and the elementary damage mechanisms. The damage variables introduced in the DMD model directly describes the local damage state of the material, as they are defined as crack densities and debonded areas. The effective macroscopic mechanical behaviour is obtained through a numerical homogenization procedure that requires the construction of representative unit cells. Specific computational tools have been developed in order to model the geometry of those unit cells and create finite element meshes of them.

The DMD model has been identified for a woven ceramic-matrix composite. It has been validated on off-axis tensile tests and its predictive capabilities have been evidenced. Although the identification of the damage kinematics requires only one on-axis tensile test, the DMD model is capable to correctly predict the tensile/shear couplings and simulate the behaviour of the materials for off-axis tests. The DMD model has also been applied to simple structural tests and has been proven to be as accurate as a reference macroscopic model. As a multiscale model, the DMD model also allows to access to the local description of the damage-driven microstructural evolution.

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